

$S_{ft}\beta^*$ - Continuous Function in Soft Topological Spaces

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Abstract:- We discussed about $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – irresolute , Strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous and Perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous in S_{ft} topological spaces. Additionally we relate the properties of these functions with other functions in S_{ft} topological spaces.

Keywords:- $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – irresolute, Strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, Perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

1. INTRODUCTION

Molodtsov[15] introduced new idea of S_{ft} set theory . It will solve the problems related to vagueness and uncertainty. Metin Akdag and Alkan Ozkan[1,3] introduced $S_{ft}\alpha$ – continuous and $S_{ft}\beta$ – continuous . From $S_{ft}\beta$ – continuous [3], we define a new definition $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous .

II. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1:[15] Let X be an initial universe and P be a set of parameters. Let $P(X)$ denote the power set of X and A be a non-empty subset of P . A pair (F, A) denoted by F_A is called a soft set over X , where F is a mapping given by $F : A \rightarrow P(X)$.

Definition 2.2:[1] Let $\tau_{S_{ft}}$ be the collection of S_{ft} sets over X , then $\tau_{S_{ft}}$ is said to be S_{ft} topology on X if it satisfies the following axioms:

- (1) \emptyset and \tilde{X} belong to τ ,
- (2) the union of any number of S_{ft} sets in $\tau_{S_{ft}}$ belongs to $\tau_{S_{ft}}$,
- (3) the intersection of any two S_{ft} sets in $\tau_{S_{ft}}$ belongs to $\tau_{S_{ft}}$.

The triplet $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}TS$ over X .

Definition 2.3:[4] A S_{ft} set (F, P) of $S_{ft}TS (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – CS if $S_{ft}int(S_{ft}cl^*(S_{ft}int((F, P))) \cong (F, P)$.

III. $S_{ft}\beta^*$ - CONTINUOUS

Definition 3.1: A S_{ft} function $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ - continuous if the inverse image of each S_{ft} – CS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$.
(ie) $f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, P))$ is a $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$, for every S_{ft} – CS (F, P) in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$.

Theorem 3.2: Every S_{ft} – continuous[8]

is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , but not conversely .

Proof : Let (F, P) be S_{ft} – CS of $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$. Given $f_{S_{ft}}$ is a S_{ft} – continuous , then $f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, P))$ is S_{ft} – CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, P))$ is a $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

Example 3.3: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_9, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_6, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_2, F_3, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not S_{ft} continuous.

Theorem 3.4: Every $S_{ft}\beta$ –continuous[3] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ –continuous, but not conversely .

Example 3.5: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_8, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_7, F_{13}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_1, F_{10}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}\beta$ –continuous.

Theorem 3.6: Every $S_{ft}b$ – continuous[2] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, but not conversely .

Example 3.7: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_4, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_5, F_{10}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_9, F_{12}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}b$ – continuous .

Theorem 3.8: Every $S_{ft}\alpha$ – continuous[1] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, but not conversely .

Example 3.9: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{11}, F_{12}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_1, F_5, F_6, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}\alpha$ – continuous.

Theorem 3.10: Every $S_{ft}S$ – continuous[11] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, but not conversely.

Example 3.11: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_{10}, F_{11}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_9, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_8, F_{10}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}S$ – continuous .

Theorem 3.12: Every $S_{ft}P$ – continuous[1] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , but not conversely .

Example 3.13: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_4, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_8, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{13}$,

$f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_2, F_{13}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}P$ – continuous.

Theorem 3.14: Every $S_{ft}g$ – continuous[12] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , but not conversely.

Example 3.15: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_5, F_{10}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_3, F_{11}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}g$ – continuous.

Theorem 3.16: Every $S_{ft}r$ – continuous[7] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, but not conversely.

Example 3.17: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_6, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{11}, F_{12}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_1, F_7, F_{11}, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}r$ – continuous .

Theorem 3.18: Every $S_{ft} S^*g$ – continuous[12] is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , but not conversely .

Example 3.19: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_9, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_1, F_6, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft} S^*g$ – continuous .

Theorem 3.20: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be a S_{ft} function from $S_{ft}TS (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ to $S_{ft}TS (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$. Then the following statements are true .

- (1) $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

(2) Inverse image of each $S_{ft} - OS$ in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* - OS$ in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$.

$$(3) \quad f_{S_{ft}} \left(S_{ft}cl \left(S_{ft}int^* \left(S_{ft}cl \left((A, P) \right) \right) \right) \right) \cong S_{ft}int \left(f \left((A, P) \right) \right) \text{ for each } S_{ft} \text{ set } (A, P) \text{ in } (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P).$$

$$(4) \quad S_{ft}cl \left(S_{ft}int^* \left(S_{ft}cl \left(f_{S_{ft}}^{-1} \left((B, Q) \right) \right) \right) \right) \cong f_{S_{ft}}^{-1} \left(S_{ft}int \left((B, Q) \right) \right) \text{ for each } S_{ft} \text{ set } (B, Q) \text{ in } (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P).$$

Corollary 3.21: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous. Then

$$(1) \quad f_{S_{ft}} \left(S_{ft}cl \left((A, P) \right) \right) \cong S_{ft}int \left(f_{S_{ft}} \left((A, P) \right) \right) \text{ for each } (A, P) \in S_{ft}S^* - C(X);$$

$$(2) \quad S_{ft}cl \left(f_{S_{ft}}^{-1} \left((B, Q) \right) \right) \cong f_{S_{ft}}^{-1} \left(S_{ft}int \left((B, Q) \right) \right) \text{ for each } (B, Q) \in S_{ft}S^* - C(Y).$$

Theorem 3.22: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $S_{ft} -$ continuous, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous.

Remark 3.23: Composition of two $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous need not be $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous.

Example 3.24: Let $X = Y = Z = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_6, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$, $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_7, F_{13}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\eta_{S_{ft}} = \{F_9, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_8, f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_9, f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_4, f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_3, f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_{10}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6, f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_7, f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_1, f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_2, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_5, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{14}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{13}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_2) = F_9, f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_{10}) = F_5, f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_5, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(X)$, so $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S\beta^* -$ continuous. Let $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $g_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_9, g_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_2, g_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_{12}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_8, g_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_{11}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6, g_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{10}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_4, g_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_1, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_7, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_5, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_3, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, g_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow g_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_1) = F_9, g_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_8) = F_4, g_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, g_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow F_4, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}$ are in $S_{ft}\beta^* - C(Y)$, so $g_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous $\Rightarrow g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is not $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous.

IV. $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ IRRESOLUTE

Definition 4.1: A S_{ft} function $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute if the inverse image of every $S_{ft}\beta^* - CS$ in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* - CS$ in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$.

Theorem 4.2: A S_{ft} function $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute iff the inverse image of every $S_{ft}\beta^* - OS$ in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* - OS$ in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P)$.

Theorem 4.3: Every $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous, but not conversely.

Example 4.4: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_6, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_{10}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_4, f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3, f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_2, f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_8, f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_{13}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_{14}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_5, f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_{12}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_1, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_9, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_6, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_7, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute.

Theorem 4.5: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $S_{ft} -$ continuous and $S_{ft} - CS$. Then $f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute.

Theorem 4.6: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be an $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute map and $g : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be an $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous, then the composition $g \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P)$ is $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ continuous.

Theorem 4.7: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be any two S_{ft} functions, then

$$(1) \quad g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P) \text{ is } S_{ft}\beta^* - \text{continuous, if } g_{S_{ft}} \text{ is soft continuous and } f_{S_{ft}} \text{ is } S_{ft}\beta^* - \text{continuous.}$$

$$(2) \quad g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, P) \text{ is } S_{ft}\beta^* - \text{irresolute, if both } f_{S_{ft}} \text{ and } g_{S_{ft}} \text{ is } S_{ft}\beta^* - \text{irresolute.}$$

Theorem 4.8: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, P) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, P)$ be $S_{ft}\beta^* -$ irresolute iff for every soft set (F, P) of X , $f_{S_{ft}} \left(S_{ft}\beta^* - cl \left((F, P) \right) \right) \subseteq S_{ft}\beta^* - cl \left(f_{S_{ft}} \left(F, P \right) \right)$.

Theorem 4.9: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -irresolute iff for all S_{ft} sets (F, \mathbb{P}) of Y , then $S_{ft}\beta^* - cl(f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, \mathbb{P}))) \subseteq f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}(S_{ft}\beta^* - cl((F, \mathbb{P})))$.

V. STRONGLY $S_{ft}\beta^*$ - CONTINUOUS

Definition 5.1: A S_{ft} function $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous if the inverse image of every $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -CS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is S_{ft} -CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$.

Theorem 5.2: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then it is S_{ft} -continuous, but not conversely.

Proof: Let (F, \mathbb{P}) be a S_{ft} -CS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \Rightarrow (F, \mathbb{P})$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -CS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$. Given $f_{S_{ft}}$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, $f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, \mathbb{P}))$ is S_{ft} -CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is S_{ft} -continuous.

Example 5.3: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau = \{F_5, F_{10}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma = \{F_9, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is S_{ft} -continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous.

Theorem 5.4: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous iff the inverse image of every $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -OS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is S_{ft} -OS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$.

Theorem 5.5: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly S_{ft} -continuous [10], then it is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, but not conversely.

Example 5.6: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5, F_6, F_7, F_8, F_{10}, F_{12}, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_3, F_{11}, F_{12}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not strongly S_{ft} -continuous.

Theorem 5.7: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then it is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, but not conversely.

Example 5.8: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_4, F_9, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_{10}, F_{11}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_2$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_3$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_7$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_9$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_8$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{14}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_{11}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{13}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{10}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous.

Theorem 5.9: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $S\beta^*$ -continuous, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is S_{ft} -continuous.

Theorem 5.10: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -irresolute, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous.

Theorem 5.11: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -irresolute.

Theorem 5.12: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous.

Theorem 5.13: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be S_{ft} -continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous.

VI. PERFECTLY $S_{ft}\beta^*$ - CONTINUOUS

Definition 6.1: A S_{ft} -function $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous if the inverse image of every $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -CS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is both S_{ft} -OS and S_{ft} -CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$.

Theorem 6.2: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, then it is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ -continuous, but not conversely.

Example 6.3: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5, F_6, F_7, F_8, F_{10}, F_{12}, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_2, F_{10}, F_{11}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_{12}$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_5$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4$, $f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_3$,

$f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_6, f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_7, f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{11}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{13}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_8, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_2, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{10}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

Theorem 6.4: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , then it is perfectly S_{ft} – continuous[10] , but not conversely .

Example 6.5: Let $X = Y = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $\tau_{S_{ft}} = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5, F_6, F_7, F_8, F_{10}, F_{12}, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$ and $\sigma_{S_{ft}} = \{F_6, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}, F_{16}\}$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be defined by $f_{S_{ft}}(F_1) = F_1, f_{S_{ft}}(F_2) = F_{12}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_3) = F_6, f_{S_{ft}}(F_4) = F_4, f_{S_{ft}}(F_5) = F_7, f_{S_{ft}}(F_6) = F_3, f_{S_{ft}}(F_7) = F_5, f_{S_{ft}}(F_8) = F_{11}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_9) = F_9, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{10}) = F_{13}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{11}) = F_8, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{12}) = F_2, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{13}) = F_{10}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{14}) = F_{14}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{15}) = F_{15}, f_{S_{ft}}(F_{16}) = F_{16} \Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is perfectly S_{ft} – continuous $\Rightarrow f_{S_{ft}}$ is not perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

Theorem 6.6: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous iff $f_{S_{ft}}^{-1}((F, \mathbb{P}))$ is both S_{ft} – OS and S_{ft} – CS in $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ for every $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – OS in $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$.

Theorem 6.7: Let $(X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be a S_{ft} – discrete topological space and $(Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be any $S_{ft}TS$. Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be S_{ft} – function , then the following statements are true .

- (1) $f_{S_{ft}}$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .
- (2) $f_{S_{ft}}$ is perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

Theorem 6.8: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ are perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous.

Theorem 6.9: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be S_{ft} – continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

Theorem 6.10: Let $f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ be perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous and $g_{S_{ft}} : (Y, \sigma_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , then $g_{S_{ft}} \circ f_{S_{ft}} : (X, \tau_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (Z, \eta_{S_{ft}}, \mathbb{P})$ is perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous .

VII.CONCLUSION

We are discussed in this paper $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous , $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – irresolute , Strongly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous, perfectly $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous . The further definitions related to $S_{ft}\beta^*$ – continuous will be discussed in my future paper.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Akdag , M ., & Alkan Ozkan , Soft α –Open sets and Soft α –Continuous functions , Abstract and Applied Analysis, vol.2014 ,7 pages , 2014 .
- [2.] Akdag , M ., & Alkan Ozkan , Soft b – Open sets and Soft b – Continuous functions , 2014 .
- [3.] Akdag , M ., & Alkan Ozkan , On Soft β –open sets and soft β –continuous functions , The Scientific World Journal , Vol-2014 , 6 pages .
- [4.] Anbarasi Rodrigo ,p., & Maheswari , S., A New Class of Soft β^* –Closed sets in Soft Topological Spaces , Paper presented in Second International Conference on Applied Mathematics And Intellectual Property Rights , pages 1-15 .
- [5.] Anbarasi Rodrigo ,P ., & Rajendra Suba , K ., Functions related to β^* –Closed sets in topological spaces , International Conference On Recent Trends In Mathematics And Information Technology, IJMTT, pp 96-100.
- [6.] Anbarasi Rodrigo ,P ., & Rajendra Suba , K ., More functions associated with β^* –continuous , (IJAETMAS), Vol-05 , Issue-02 , pp.47-56 .
- [7.] Christy, V., & Mohana , K., On Soft πGP – Continuous functions in Soft topological spaces, International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing , Vol-6, Issue no.8, pp.2605-2610, 2016.
- [8.] Cigdem Gunduz Aras , Ayse Sonmez , Huseyin Cakalli , On Soft Mapping , May 2013 .
- [9.] Gnanachandra , P ., & Lellis Thivagar , M ., A New Notion of Star Open Sets in Soft Topological Spaces , World Scientific News (An International Scientific Journal), WSN 144, pp. 196-207 , 2020.
- [10.] Jackson , Pious Missier , S., & Anbarasi Rodrigo , P., Soft Strongly JP Continuous Functions , Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics , ISSN 0973-1768 , Vol-13 , no.5,2017 .
- [11.] Juthika Mahanta & Pramod Kumar Das , On Soft Topological Space via Semi – Open and Semi-Closed Soft sets , KYUNGPOOK Math.J., 54(2014),pp.221-236 .
- [12.] Kannan , K., Rajalakshmi , D., Gopikrishnan , B., Janani , R., & Madhumitha , M., Soft S^*g –Continuous Functions , International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics , Vol-119,no.6,pp.51-61,2018 .
- [13.] Kannan , K., Soft Generalized Closed Sets in Soft Topological Spaces , Journal Of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology , Vol-37, No.1,pp.17-21,2012.

- [14.] Kannan ,K., Rajalakshmi,D ., & Srikanth, R., Soft rg^{**} –Closed Sets , International Journal Of Pure And Applied Mathematics , Vol-119,No.6,pp.39-49,2018.
- [15.] Molodtsov , D., Soft set theory – first results , Computers and Mathematics with Applications , Vol-37,No.4-5,pp.19-31,1999.
- [16.] Sasikala , V.E., & Sivaraj,D., On Soft Semi-Open Sets , International Journal Of Management and Applied Science , Vol-3,Issue-9,2017.
- [17.] Yuksel ,S., Tozlu ,N., & Ergul , Z.G., Soft regular generalized closed sets in Soft Topological Spaces , International Journal of Mathematical Analysis , 8(2014), 355-367.